

Just participation in wind energy: The role of social innovations

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ABSTRACT

Participatory practices and social innovations are recognised as important for sustainable renewable energy projects. However, information on the significance of diverse participatory practices and social innovations for advancing inclusive and sustainable wind energy developments remains limited. To address this gap, this study aims to understand how diverse participatory practices in wind energy developments across the globe influence energy justice differently. It does so, by analysing how a fairer participation of communities is interconnected to the models of participation while investigating how participatory practices interrelate with social innovations. Drawing on the ‘ecologies of participation’ approach, the work compiles a dataset of 312 case studies of collective participatory practices in wind energy projects, of which 209 are classified as social innovation projects. Findings indicate that not all participatory practices and social innovations are equal in ensuring just processes in wind energy governance. This requires careful consideration of different aspects of participation (e.g., opportunities provided, continuity of the process) and adherence to principles of justice in wind energy governance (e.g., inclusivity, capacity to influence, transparency). Conclusions highlight that fairer participation practices are interconnected to both the models of participation and to the wider spaces of participation in which they are embedded.

1. Introduction

The governance of energy transformations requires careful consideration of procedural, distributional and recognition justice aspects [1, 2], which offers an overarching framing for this study. Despite a large body of evidence on the relationships between participation, social acceptance of renewable energy technologies [3] and a just energy transition [4], there remains a lack of thorough characterisation of the variety of practices, and their interrelation to energy justice principles, through which citizens and communities are involved in renewable energy projects [5,6].

Wind energy participatory practices are conceptualised as “ecologies”, linked to specific material and immaterial objects (e.g., a wind farm, a new legal framework) and involving diverse subjects (e.g., residents, policymakers, investors) [7]. Participatory practices may be enacted through various models of engagement [7] such as public

hearings, or general assemblies, but can also include citizen protests. Nevertheless, participatory practices do not always consistently adhere to principles of procedural justice, such as inclusivity, empowerment, and transparency [1]. They can range from token or alibi participation to financial participation and cooperation practices, and occur at multiple moments, providing diverse opportunities for participation or being limited to a one-time event [8,9].

The novelty of the study lies in its reflection on the interrelations between collective participatory practices and a just wind energy governance, with a specific focus on practices undertaken by social innovations (SI). By departing from the “ecologies of participation” framework [7], this analysis evidences how different models of participation contribute to energy justice in diverse contexts, drawing on empirical examples from across the globe. In addition, the analysis investigates the specific relevance of SI, as subjects of participation [7,10] in fostering an inclusive and transparent energy transition [11].

Abbreviations: Renewable Energy Cooperatives (REScoops), Social Innovations (SI).

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Thus, the key contribution of this work lies in understanding how diverse participatory practices in wind energy developments across the globe influence energy justice differently. This is explored through two interrelated exploratory hypotheses: First, higher opportunities for the participation of communities are closely linked to the models of participation employed. Second, projects driven by social innovation initiatives are more likely to exhibit inclusive and transparent participatory practices, which are essential for achieving (wind) energy justice [12,13].

SI encompass novel ideas, practices, and organisational arrangements with the potential to challenge existing norms and power structures, and therefore to cater to energy justice principles [14]. As a critical societal response to complex environmental challenges [15], SI are perceived as potentially “transformative” for advancing socio-technical transitions [16,17]. They can facilitate energy access, encourage the co-production of knowledge, and promote energy democracy and participatory processes that contribute to just energy transitions [10].

To address its hypotheses, the analysis takes stock of an original dataset, collected by the authors [18], of 312 cases of wind energy projects, 209 of which were considered to be led by SI [19]. Data was collated through a review and analysis of approximately 500 documents throughout 2023, including examples from across the globe, although most are from Europe and North America. Focussing on wind energy allows for an examination of participatory practices within a well-established yet contested renewable energy technology sector [20], particularly as it encounters the entrance of emerging technologies, such as offshore floating wind [21].

The analysis is structured in six sections. The subsequent section describes the concepts guiding the data collection and analysis (Section 2), followed by a description of the methods and materials used (Section 3). Section 4 presents the results, including an overview of the case studies collected and their participatory practices. Results are discussed in Section 5 while Section 6 offers a conclusion with guidelines for future research, policy and practice.

2. Ecologies of participation, energy justice and social innovations

Conceptually, the study takes a systemic and relational approach, cutting across sustainability transitions research in the scope of energy participation and social innovation studies [7,17]. In this literature, Chilvers and his colleagues [7] introduce the “ecologies of participation” framework, which understands participation systems as being shaped by both political cultures and institutional settings, and participatory practices to be embedded in wider socio-technical systems [22]. Using this framework enables moving beyond an analysis of community participation in energy as isolated activities to characterise the dynamics and interrelations of such participation practices. Participatory practices are conceptualised along three constituting elements [7] (p.201), namely: the procedures for engagement, or “models” (e.g., a citizen jury), the “subjects” of engagement (e.g. a farmers community) and the “objects” of engagement (e.g., a wind park, a new policy). These models, subjects and objects of participation are characterised as being “actively co-produced” (p. 201) through collective practices framed within “wider spaces of participation” (p.202) wherein participatory practices interconnect. The framework equally emphasises the relevance of institutions, governance, political and regulatory frameworks, and established relations between diverse actor groups collectively advancing with energy projects, proposing that these form “systemic constitutional stabilities” (p. 202). These energy constitutions can be interpreted as a dominant socio-technical regime [23], as they are established and continuously reinforced by legal frameworks, policy and governance, while also being subject to transformative change.

By characterising collective participatory practices (i.e., grounded on models, subjects, and objects); wider spaces of participation, and

energy-as-constitution, Chilvers and colleagues’ framework highlights the co-constructed interrelations between participatory practices and institutions. For instance, the authors refer to policy deliberations on nuclear energy in the United Kingdom, for which the participation “model” was a deliberative public engagement process, the “subjects” involved were the public participants, activists and experts, and the “object” was the issue of nuclear energy and its governance. Media debates about climate change were considered wider spaces of participation, whereas nuclear power is an important element of the country’s energy infrastructure and policy, and, therefore, part of its “energy constitution”. However, the work of Chilvers and colleagues is limited to the United Kingdom, with no link to procedural, distributive, and recognition justice aspects [2,9].

Thus, this study advances this research by explicitly exploring the interrelations between different models (i.e., consultation practices, community funds, etc.), objects (i.e., wind energy technology), and subjects of participation (including the special case of SI initiatives), considering the extent to which these elements enable an inclusive, transparent and influential engagement of citizens and communities, with examples from across the globe. The application of the ecologies of participation framework to this study is illustrated in Fig. 1.

In addition, when subjects of participation include vulnerable communities (e.g., Indigenous Peoples), aspects of distributive justice (i.e., how the costs and benefits of wind projects are distributed) and recognition justice (i.e., who is (not) listened to nor included in the discussion) comes to the foreground [24]. Thus, this study offers an enquiry into procedural justice in the context of wind energy, while also reflecting on interrelated distributive and recognition justice aspects.

In the scope of the models of participation [7], the research provided critical insights for considering energy justice principles. Proposed typologies include the well-known Arnstein’s “Ladder of Participation” [25] and Pretty’s “Typology of Participation” [26]. Arnstein’s Ladder identifies eight levels of participation based on how citizens can influence decision-making, while Pretty’s typology is concerned with how different models of participation impact project outcomes. Aiken’s research [27] explores the role of trust and participation in wind energy projects, emphasising that mere information provision is not sufficient to ensure public support and that consultation and cooperation models are critical to address stakeholder concerns. Jobert and colleagues [28] compare wind energy development in different European countries to conclude that models such as consultation and cooperation lead to less opposition. Wüstenhagen and colleagues [29] evidence that financial participation mechanisms, such as community ownership, enhance local acceptance of wind energy projects.

Research has also demonstrated that cooperation models can be more inclusive than mere financial and/or economic participation, as the latter may imply limited opportunities for engagement and involve a small group of stakeholders (e.g., land lease payments, and in-kind payments). Some studies suggest that models, such as compensation payments, may be perceived as “bribes” and do not always entail active community participation [7,30]. In contrast, cooperation requires the active participation of citizens and communities, often throughout a project’s life cycle, from the early planning to construction and even decommissioning stages. In renewable energy cooperatives (REScoops), for instance, cooperative members collectively decide on the investments to be undertaken [31].

Studies have likewise recognised the role of resistance initiatives and networks [32,33] as one participatory practice. Community opposition to projects may be pursued through petitions, legal processes, or online discussions through social media. However, the causes of opposition are thought to often lie in issues of social (in)justice and environmental protection, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of energy justice aspects [34,35].

Informed by this research, the diverse models of participation of the collected cases were classified into six levels of participation, namely: alibi participation (citizens wish to engage in wind energy projects but

Fig. 1. Application of the ecologies of participation to collect information on wind energy participation practices.

their participation is ineffective, as their opinions, concerns and suggestions are disregarded or inconsequential for the final decision); informational participation (a type of involvement through activities that offer rare opportunities to influence decisions); opposition (when communities are actively opposed to a wind energy project, and seek to exert their influence); consultative participation (entailing the active participation and expression of opinions); financial participation (involvement of citizens and communities, through their financial investment or benefits received from wind energy projects); and cooperation (jointly deciding on wind energy plans through collaborative decision-making processes).

Furthermore, social innovation initiatives are considered subjects of participation and perceived as catalysts for transformative changes in societal systems, such as the energy transition [17]. Often, these initiatives imply the participation of civil society and third-sector organisations and introduce new ways of doing and organising, possibly fostering new social values and social sustainability [14]. Thus, this analysis equally considers participatory practices as important to Social Innovations (SI), themselves emerging through wider stakeholder networks that frame their ability to foster socio-technical change [17,36].

Examples of SI in the energy sector include municipalities collaborating with citizen associations, member-owned non-profit energy cooperatives, and Indigenous communities striving for greater energy autonomy through grassroots renewable energy projects [19,37,38]. SI have been relevant to energy justice research topics, such as gender equality in the energy system, energy poverty, and energy democracy concerns [39–41]. SI equally include new engagement practices and new mechanisms for financial participation [12]. Likewise, they have played a role in incentivising new policies or evaluating existing regulatory frameworks for community participation in wind energy [42,43].

Hewitt and colleagues' historical review of these initiatives in the energy sector [19] led to a classification of SI based on their organisational forms. The key criteria for their classification included the emergence of crises and opportunities (i.e., leading to an increased awareness of energy issues and the mobilisation of citizens); the agency of civil society (i.e., SI often emerged through the efforts of civil society actors); reconfiguration of social practices, institutions and networks (i.

e., SI challenge predominant practices and instigate new networks and institutions); and, consequently, new ways of working.

Based on these criteria, the organisational forms of SI identified by the authors include "REScoops" (renewable energy cooperatives); "community development trusts or funds" (a company invests, with at least part of the revenues managed by a local community trust); "local government projects with citizen participation" (partnerships between municipalities and local associations or cooperatives to invest in projects); "public-private partnerships" (cooperatives or other social economy models partnering with companies); "private companies" (companies associated with a cooperative for energy distribution, or other social economy models); and "other grassroots initiatives" [19].

Hewitt and colleagues' classification of SI does not account for differences among grassroots initiatives. These are defined as a "set of practices initiated by formal or informal community-led initiatives or/and social movements" that "aim to generate novel, democratic, socially, spatially and environmentally just solutions to address social needs that are otherwise ignored or marginalised" [44] (p.146). Examples of grassroots initiatives range from communities' direct participation in renewable energy production [45] to local opposition to renewable energy projects [46,47]. Therefore, this analysis distinguishes between "grassroots projects" and "grassroots opposition" as two types of grassroots innovations. The former refers to grassroots initiatives either acting individually or establishing local partnerships to develop new energy projects. The latter is characterised by resistance initiatives to renewable wind energy projects, either formally or informally organised, due to perceived socioeconomic and/or environmental negative impacts. Fig. 2 summarises this study's key concepts for analysing collective participatory practices. As shown in the figure, the ecologies of participation framework provides a lens for collecting and analysing participatory practices and their relationship to social innovations. The data analysis includes social innovation initiatives as subjects of participation, while the classification of these innovations draws on the work of Hewitt and colleagues.

Fig. 2. Mind map of the relationship between concepts for analysing collective participatory practices.

3. Materials and methods

This review study is an analysis of a compilation of case studies of participation retrieved through a review of documents on wind energy developments. The analysis employs a qualitative and quantitative approach to investigate its two interrelated hypotheses, namely that higher opportunities for the participation of communities are closely linked to the models of participation employed, and that projects driven by social innovation initiatives are more likely to exhibit inclusive and transparent participatory practices.

A dataset [18] of participatory practices in wind energy was developed, and subsequently built upon through qualitative and quantitative methods [48]. Data collection, employing web scraping techniques (i.e., surveying websites to collect and store freely available information) [49] and data analysis took stock of open-source code, namely Python libraries [50], openly accessible for reuse and reproducibility. When applied, web scraping techniques did not involve the collection of private data. Data was only collected when available on websites which, for instance, gathered information about community energy projects and did not include the means for direct downloading of such information (e.g., RESCOOP. EU and Community Energy England websites).

Cases depicting participation were determined based on the presence of keywords referencing participation in the collected corpus of documents such as “engagement”, “involvement”, “social innovation”, “energy community”, among others. These words were based on the synonyms developed by Chilvers et al. [7], while additional words/synonyms were added in the six languages used for the search and analysis (i.e., English, Dutch, German, French, Portuguese and Spanish).

The sample of documents for review was compiled through three search rounds across diverse data sources, namely Scopus and Google Scholar (for research articles); Cordis (a database of European-funded projects) [51]; ProQuest (database of news media and blog articles) [52], community energy networks (e.g. RESCOOP. EU, Community Energy England) [53,54] and the Global Wind Power Tracker Wiki [55]. A search protocol guided the retrieval of the first pool of eligible documents, using the following keywords in the different web data sources: “wind energy”; “wind energy AND participation”; “case studies”; “wind energy AND community”, “wind energy AND social innovation”. For each document selected, additional information was collected when

necessary, through a snowballing approach, by following up on the reviewed document’s references.

Exclusion criteria for the documents sampled included (i) documents which contained contradictory or erroneous information; (ii) documents which did not specifically refer to wind energy and (iii) documents which were not related to specific wind energy projects (i.e., case studies), or which did not describe any aspects related to participation and citizens’ engagement in the context of specific wind energy projects. Further inclusion criteria were (i) the salience (innovation of the project due to the communities involved or the participatory process); (ii) reliability of information (information was clear, based on reliable sources and factchecked), and (iii) the description of how citizens and communities were involved in a wind energy project.

From a first pool of 1145 documents eligible for review, a sample of 700 documents was selected through initial screening (based on the first two exclusion criteria). A final sample of 500 documents was created while considering all exclusion and inclusion criteria. Information on 312 cases was manually collected from this sample of documents after eliminating duplicates (as some documents referred to the same participation case). Thus, the final dataset analysed in this study encompasses 312 case studies, including 209 cases which were led by social innovation initiatives in the energy sector.

The participation cases were collected from several information sources [56]. The diversity of information sources implies different degrees of validity. However, all cases retrieved from non-academic sources were fact-checked, ensuring, as much as possible, the validity of the information, based on how dependable sources were and cross-checking facts. For instance, if blog posts were the first source of information, additional sources were sought out, such as new media articles, and governmental and official documents related to e.g., permitting procedures and environmental impact assessments.

Thus, the information sources to characterise the case studies included 91 (29 %) journal articles, 62 (19 %) community websites, 54 (17 %) wikis, 48 (15 %) European project deliverables, 22 (7 %) investigative journalism news media, 18 (5 %) blog posts, 9 (2 %) other types of reports and 8 (2 %) academic theses. The sample of cases (represented in Fig. 3) is distributed across 41 countries, divided into Northern Europe (80 cases), Western Europe (52 cases), North America (48 cases); Southern Europe (33 cases); Central Europe (31 cases); South

Fig. 3. Source of the documents collected (left) and region of the case studies (right).

America (20 cases); Eastern Europe (19 cases); Asia (11 cases); Australia (10 cases); and Africa (8 cases). European and American regions were subdivided to reflect the diversity of the sampled cases. However, due to the small sample of African, Australian, and Asian cases, these were not further subdivided into continental regions.

To capture the variety of information provided for each participation case, the dataset comprises 49 variables (the full database is available at a public repository [18]). However, only 11 selected variables, described in Table 1, were used in this analysis.

After collecting a sample of cases studies, the specific models, subjects, and objects of participation were identified for each collected practice, reflecting the ecologies of participation framework. The thematic coding of the diverse participation models was based on the revised documents, and further refined inductively through the first forty case studies collected. However, capturing the systemic constitutional stabilities and broader spaces of participation proved challenging due to the diversity of the countries represented in the example. The participation models were categorised into six levels of participation, defined using research evidence regarding how these levels (e.g., cooperation, consultation) align with energy justice principles of inclusivity, transparency, and influence [25,28,42].

Thus, the levels of participation provide an overarching assumption for this study. Although these levels are based on scholarly research and were jointly discussed and agreed upon by the team, they inevitably carry some degree of subjectivity. For instance, cooperation could be seen by others as involving a less active role for participants compared to financial and economic participation. To determine the appropriate level for each case, the reviewed sources were used to identify the most relevant level of participation documented. For instance, in case 1, cited in Table 2 (results), the source clearly referred to pro-forma and alibi forms of participation. Additionally, the “opportunities” variable was coded based on the researchers’ interpretation. As such, the study’s results should be considered with these underlying assumptions in mind. Nevertheless, all entries were cross validated by at least two researchers involved in collecting and classifying the case studies, with additional documents consulted as needed to further validate the classifications.

Qualitative analysis was employed in the coding and interpreting of the collected data, allowing for their classification into qualitative and ordinal variables (e.g., opportunities for participation, etc.). Quantitative analysis was conducted using open-source Python code. The main Python libraries used were Pandas, Numpy, Statsmodels and Scikit-learn

for data analysis (i.e., descriptive and inferential statistics) [50], as well as Matplotlib and Seaborn (for data visualisation) [57].

Descriptive statistics included determining descriptive measures, such as means, medians, frequency and standard deviation values [58]. In addition, correlation coefficients were calculated. The variables analysed included the ordinal variable “level score”; the “timing score”; and the “opportunities score”. Pearson correlation coefficients were utilised to assess linear relationships. To explore correlations between ordinal variables whenever Pearson assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity were not met, Spearman coefficients were employed [59]. The directionality of the correlations, whether positive or negative, was also considered in the interpretation.

In the case of the “capacity” variable, which represents the installed wind energy capacity in each case, there were significant outliers due to the wide range of projects, from national to local levels. To facilitate analysis using this variable, outliers at both the lower and upper range were removed. Outliers were calculated based on the interquartile range (i.e., by multiplying 1.5 by the first quartile to define a lower bound, and 1.5 by the third quartile to define an upper bound).

To explore statistically significant trends between the level of participation and opportunities for participation, the ordered logit model was chosen due to the ordinal nature of the dependent variable [60]. This model captures the ordered relationship between the opportunities for participation and the predictor variable (i.e. “level score”). It accounts for the likelihood of falling into higher categories (i.e., with higher opportunities for participation) while recognising the ordered ranks in the response variable. Additionally, the ordered logit provides insights into how changes in the predictor variable affect the probability of each outcome (i.e., higher or lower opportunities for participation). However, logit models are sensitive to outliers, which can distort the results [60]. Therefore, outliers were removed before running the model, reducing the number of observations to 260.

3.1. Limitations

This study is subject to methodological and geographical limitations. First, the characterisation of the collected cases relies solely on information from written documents and online sources, as there was no direct validation with those involved in the various examples collected. Exceptions include research articles and deliverables from European research projects, which are validated sources. A second, related

Table 1
Key variables characterising each analysed case study.

Variable Name	Description	Options/Range	Data Type
Technology	Type of technology	Small Wind, Onshore Wind, Offshore Wind, Onshore and Offshore	Nominal
Scale	Scale of governance of the case study	Local, Regional, National, Transnational	Nominal
Capacity	Installed capacity in Mega Watt (MW)/year.	Value of installed capacity in MW	Continuous
Social Innovation	In case of a social innovation, the case study was classified based on organisational forms.	REScoops, Grassroots Opposition, Grassroots Projects, Local Gov. with Citizens, Community Trust/Fund, Private Company, Public-Private, Not Social Innovation	Nominal
Level of Participation	Ordered level of participation	Alibi, Information, Opposition, Consultation, Financial/Economic, Cooperation	Nominal
Level Score	Score of the level of participation	1 to 6	Ordinal
Legal Obligation	Existing obligation for participation	Not applicable, Legal Mandate, Voluntary	Nominal
Stage of Project	Stage of the project at which participation occurred	Exploration/Ideation, Planning, Construction, Maintenance, Decommissioning, More than one stage, Throughout the project	Nominal
Timing Score	Number of times participation occurred	1 (one stage), 2 (more than one stage), 3 (throughout the project)	Ordinal
Opportunities	Quality of the participatory process	Insufficient, Sufficient, Moderate, Good, Excellent	Nominal
Opportunities Score	Based on quality of the participatory process, but with a numeric value assigned.	1 to 5	Ordinal

limitation is the varying standards of accuracy across the diverse sources used. Third, assessing the depth of the participatory process based solely on documentary evidence is challenging without the unique, direct perspectives of those involved [61]. While this approach may result in the loss of some qualitative data, the database enables the screening of a wide range of cases, which can later be explored through in-depth qualitative analysis and anthropological field research.

Fourth, there is a geographical predominance of European countries, followed by North American countries (United States and Canada) which reflects the documentation available (e.g., research articles, databases) with sufficient details to characterise a specific entry into the database. The data collection regarding research projects took Europe as a starting point, while the search for research articles to be reviewed had a wider global scope. Nevertheless, Global South project descriptions are less present in research articles, news media and other sources used. However, the analysis did not directly address comparative differences

between regions, as this is not the focus of the study’s hypotheses.

4. Results

The results address the study’s hypotheses by characterising collective participation practices and the predominant models that underpin these practices. This includes the analysis of specific cases, statistical relationships and the role of SI in relation to participation.

The year of the construction of the installations of the collected cases range from 1980 to 2026. Future years indicate cases where the planned construction has yet to occur, although earlier exploration and ideation stages have already taken place. Most projects were constructed between 2010 and 2022, while most documentary sources were published between 2017 and 2023. The case studies retrieved included 152 examples at the local level, 109 at the regional level, 46 national, and five transnational (involving more than one country). Regarding the use of technology, 246 cases are onshore wind projects, 47 concern offshore wind, and 13 are small wind projects (i.e., with an installed capacity equal to or lower than one MWh). Six projects include both onshore and offshore wind energy installations. Fig. 4 illustrates distribution data, related to the technology and the scale of governance. The scale was determined based on whether the project involved predominantly the participation of local actors (village, city), regional, national or at transnational actors.

All case studies referenced are taken from the compiled dataset of 312 cases [23]. To illustrate the variety of cases, 20 examples of collective participation practices, including their subjects, objects and the identified models are provided in Table 2.

4.1. What models of participation are most common in wind energy?

The reviewed documents highlight a primary level of participation based on the information presented in the collected documentation. Considering the main level characterising the case studies, “Consultation” practices constitute the largest group (82 cases; 26 %), followed by “Financial and Economic” participation (76 cases; 24 %); “Cooperation” (56 cases; 17 %); “Opposition” (45 cases; 14 %); “Information” (38 cases; 12 %); and “Alibi” participation, which comprises only 4 % of the sampled cases (15 cases). However, practices are also interrelated to other levels of participation in 119 cases. For instance, when the predominant level of participation was cooperation, 33 cases included also practices of financial and economic participation. Similarly, when consultation was the main level of participation, there were 15 case studies in which information practices were also present. In opposition cases, there were no cooperation practices, yet there were nine financial practices (including four cases of compensation payments, three land lease cases, a tax revenue, and a community fund case). Therefore, the levels of participation are indicative only of the main model that characterises the case study, as diverse practices co-exist, interrelated to local community responses and contexts.

The case studies include 43 participation models, which were inductively identified based on the documentary evidence. Regarding these models, citizen investments, general assemblies and community ownership are the most common. These three practices are shared by the financial/economic and cooperation levels, as illustrated by the mind map presented in Fig. 5, which also offers a mapping of the 43 identified models.

In the context of alibi participation, community action agencies seek to secure community acceptance of new projects by presenting established plans to the populations without actively encouraging dialogue. An illustrative example can be found in Brazil in the Nordeste region, where 930 wind parks already exist, supported significantly by the government to promote wind energy expansion through multinational energy companies (i.e., Iberdola, Enel Green and Volitalia from Spain, Italy, and France, respectively). These companies established long-term (25–50 years) land lease contracts with local landowners, who the

Table 2
Summary Information on 20 cited examples of participatory practices.

Title	Source	Year (case)	Reference	Country	Subjects	Tech (objects)	Level/Model
1. Simón et al., 2019 (Galicia)	Journal article	2009	[62]	Spain	Government, Municipality Investors	Onshore Wind (turbines)	Alibi (pro forma)
2. Armeni, 2016 (England case)	Journal article	2016	[42]	United Kingdom	Community Government Municipality Experts Investors	Offshore Wind (new plant, company)	Consultation (community committee)
3. Armeni, 2016 (Wales case)	Journal article	2016	[42]	United Kingdom	Community Government Municipality	Onshore Wind (new wind farm, company)	Consultation (community committee)
4. Karam and Shokrgozar, 2023 (Sámi people)	Journal article	2021	[63]	Norway	Indigenous Peoples (Sámi) Government Investors	Onshore Wind (turbines, indigenous rights)	Opposition (protests, legal action)
5. Quality label “Fair Wind Park Planner”	Report – EU project	2019	[13]	Germany	Experts Investors	Onshore Wind (policy, company)	Information (quality label)
6. Ocean (Ørsted) wind farm	Wiki	2024	[64]	United States	Community of Interest Investors Experts, Municipality Government	Offshore Wind (new plant)	Information (news media, presentation)
7. Apple Blossom wind farm	Wiki	2017	[65]	United States	Community Trust/Fund Municipality Investors	Onshore Wind (turbines)	Financial (community fund)
8. MinWind I-IX wind farms	Wiki	2002	[66]	United States	Community Trust/Fund Farmers Government	Onshore Wind	Cooperation (community ownership)
9. Pukwis Community Wind Park	Wiki	2011	[67]	Canada	Grassroots project Indigenous Peoples (Chippewas First Nation)	Onshore Wind	Cooperation (community ownership)
10. Viure del Aire	Website	2009	[68]	Spain	Private Company, Local community NGO	Onshore Wind (turbines)	Financial (community ownership)
11. Vent d’engan	Website	2019	[69]	Belgium	REScoop Small investors	Onshore Wind (turbines)	Financial (community ownership/general assembly)
12. EcoPower	Website	1992	[70]	Belgium	REScoop Municipality Small investors	Onshore Wind (turbines, energy policy)	Financial (citizen investors/general assembly)
13. Hyndburn Wind Farm	Website	2012	[71]	United Kingdom	Community Trust/Fund	Onshore Wind (new wind farm, role of community)	Financial (community fund)
14. Biigtong Dbenjgan	Website	2002	[72]	Canada	Grassroots Project Indigenous Peoples (Ojibway) Investors	Onshore Wind (new wind farm, role of community)	Cooperation (community ownership/trusted third-party)
15. Citizens’ juries: wind farm Scotland	News media	2015	[73]	United Kingdom	Community of interest Experts	Offshore Wind (planning wind farms)	Consultation (citizen juries)
16. Belgium Offshore Platform	News media	2021	[74]	Belgium	NGO Government Investors	Offshore Wind (biodiversity protection)	Cooperation (working group)
17. Zeewolde Wind Farm	News media	2020	[75]	Netherlands	Community of interest Small investors	Onshore Wind (wind farm)	Financial (community ownership)
18. Brazil (Nordeste Region)	News media	2022	[76]	Brazil	Farmers Government Investors	Onshore Wind (turbines, rural community)	Alibi (community action agencies)
19. Burchill Wind Project	Blog post	2020	[77]	Canada	Public-Private Partnership Indigenous Peoples (Mi’kmaq) Investors	Onshore Wind (turbines)	Financial (community fund)
20. Multilab Project (MIRACL)	Blog post	2017	[78]	United States	Local community Experts Investors	Onshore Wind (turbines, rural community)	Cooperation (transdisciplinary committee)

companies’ local subsidiaries presented with a final plan, to which landowners were not invited to contribute. The situation led to significant controversy and accusations of “green grabbing” [79] as traditional farmers were disposed of their land use. Traldi’s PhD thesis on this case study points to potential contractual frauds in the attribution of licenses to large investors [80]. Investigative journalism articles [76] equally contested this private appropriation of wind and its consequences for the livelihoods of traditional farming communities.

Pro forma legal processes are implemented when public consultation processes are mandatory. One example comes from Galicia in Spain, where the development of wind energy between 1995 and 2009 was characterised by a legal framework which enabled the expropriation of landowners under the guise of “public utility”. In this context, local

populations, legally required to be informed about the projects, could not influence decisions [62].

Participation practices based on informing communities about planned projects include project websites, organised presentations of projects, news media stories, and education activities. A key distinction between information and alibi participation is the opportunity for feedback and the intent to inform citizens while ensuring transparency about the project. The “Fair Wind Park Planner” label for project planners and developers in Schleswig-Holstein is an example of a “quality label” designed in the context of wind energy production [13]. The label was developed by the Wind Energy Technology Institute of Flensburg University (Germany) in partnership with an expert advisory group. To attain the label, companies must comply with specific guidelines based

Fig. 4. The technology of the case studies collected and the scale of governance.

Fig. 5. Models of participation retrieved from 312 cases.

on criteria such as the provision of information about the project, as well as participatory practices, including offering the possibility for financial participation. Thus, although considered an example of information, projects which attain this label are expected to have committed to a wide range of processes of participation.

Another case of information participation in New Jersey was the Ocean Wind 1 and 2 planned by the renewable energy Ørsted company. Information about the project (which was planned for 2024) was largely

provided through a website, public presentations, and local media. The project included two offshore wind farms which were supposed to become the first offshore wind farms in the region and came with promises of economic benefits. Ultimately, both farms were cancelled by the promoters in January 2024 [64].

Collective opposition practices include protests, legal actions, campaigns, and petitions. In Norway, protests of representatives of the Sámi People and environmental activists (including climate activist Greta

Thunberg) targeted two wind farms built on Sámi reindeer grazing fields. According to Sámi representatives, traditional reindeer herding practices were threatened by a large onshore wind farm (i.e., 151 turbines, up to 86 m high). Protests took place one year after the Sámi People achieved a winning victory in Norway's Supreme Court (which ruled that the wind farm permits violated the rights of Sámi communities), due to a lack of response or action from the project promoters following the court ruling. The court's decision did not entail removing the wind turbines, and promoters opted to negotiate solutions with the community to make it possible to keep the turbines. Protests are thus grounded on an underlying issue of injustice well described by the Political Advisor to the Sámi Parliament in Norway to CNN, who stated that "Indigenous Peoples are asked to give up their lands for the wind industry, mining, and other purposes to save the world from a crisis mainly created by others" [81].

Various consultation practices were identified. Community committees, for instance, are legally mandated consultation processes that project promoters must organise. These committees are required to provide populations with detailed information about the project, while also allowing the public to express their opinions. Armeni [42] analyses two illustrative case studies of an offshore and an onshore wind project in England and Wales. He concludes that, while community committees facilitate community participation in decision-making, they are insufficient to ensure that community values and interests are effectively considered and to safeguard the integration of the community's objectives into the project's implementation. Armeni's research emphasises how "participation as deliberative public dialogue and influence clashes fundamentally with a model of public acceptance, whereby participants are simply asked to accept and validate decisions already made" (p.174) [42]. "Citizen Juries" offer an innovative consultation method, although it was only found in one case, in the context of a research project. In this case, three diverse groups of citizens were tasked with agreeing on principles and developing criteria for decision-making about onshore wind farms in Scotland. While applied in a research context, the method drew on real-life wind farms located in the regions where the participating citizen groups were gathered, and feedback was provided to project promoters.

Financial and economic participation practices include diverse models through which citizens take up the role of prosumers [82], but also of beneficiaries of the investments. For instance, the Zeewolde wind farm project in the Netherlands involved the repowering of 220 turbines, financed by bank loans, with the participation of over 200 local farmers, residents, and entrepreneurs. The process led to tripling the previously installed capacity. The business model is based on a long-term Power Purchase Agreement for renewable electricity to provide economic returns to the community while paying investors. Minwind is also a farmers' community case from Minnesota, considered the first farmer community-owned wind power plant in the United States. The project started in 2002, although early ideas emerged in 1999, as an investment by farmers to generate extra income. The community owns nine wind farm projects. The business model is based on dividends received by members based on how much has been invested, after selling the produced energy to a local utility.

Cooperatives like Eco-Power and SeaCoop (a Belgium-based offshore wind cooperative in which Eco-Power participates) are the most common legal form of community in the collected examples. Community funds are another innovative practice, enabling communities to participate as beneficiaries of projects. In the United States, the Apple Blossom Wind Farm (Michigan) established a \$20,000 annual community fund for local charity community projects. The fund is managed by a community-led board of directors and engages independent volunteers.

Cooperation practices include general assemblies, the most common practice of cooperation linked to the REScoops included in the data. General assemblies were included when explicitly referenced as spaces for deliberation, although in most countries, cooperatives legally require approval of their accounts and internal documents from a general

assembly. Less common practices include working groups and trans-disciplinary committees. For example, in the United States, the trans-disciplinary committee entitled MIRACL (i.e., Microgrids, Infrastructure Resilience, and Advanced Controls Launchpad) was launched by the US Department of Energy Wind Technologies to bring renewable energy to remote communities, such as St Mary's, Alaska, through distributed wind energy production. The committee collected and analysed data by engaging local committee members, benefiting from their expert and traditional knowledge, to develop a local plan for wind energy in the remote region's microgrid that would effectively meet community needs. The cooperation occurred at the ideation and planning stages, demonstrating an action-research approach for implementing renewables in remote areas. The committee has also involved traditional and Indigenous communities, facilitating knowledge co-production and integrating local community needs in energy planning [78].

An example of a trusted third party as a cooperation practice comes from Canada's First Nations, namely the Ojibway, who founded the Biigtigong Dbenjgan energy, forestry, and construction organisation, which includes two wind farms, along with investments in hydropower, biofuels, and the development of microgrids. Guided by environmental stewardship, the companies' investments entail the development of partnerships to cooperate with other organisations and companies. The organisation re-invests profits from projects back into the Biigtigong community.

Lastly, the Belgium Offshore Platform is an example of a working group with the participation of diverse parties, including environmental organisations (e.g., Greenpeace Belgium; WWF-Belgium) and private investors to protect biodiversity in North Sea offshore wind energy developments [83]. Compared to informational and consultation practices, cooperation and financial participation practices are more inclusive, directly engaging communities and citizens while providing direct social and economic benefits.

4.2. How often are participatory practices adopted?

Across global wind energy developments, participatory practices vary from ideation to planning and final decommissioning. In 170 (54 %) cases, participation took place only once (e.g., a single moment for public consultation). Concerning the specific stages, participation took place during the planning stage in 79 cases (25 %), and throughout the project's life cycle in 71 cases (22 %), mostly corresponding to REScoops (69 cases). After planning, the second most common stage for participation was early exploration and ideation (37 cases, 11 %), followed by the maintenance stage, (9 %), construction (7 %), and only one case during decommissioning. These findings are presented in Fig. 6.

Opportunities for participation, as shown in Fig. 7, were classified from "insufficient" to "excellent". In 144 (46 %) cases, opportunities for participation were rated as moderate, in 65 cases (20 %) as excellent, and 62 cases (19 %) as insufficient. Comparing pre-existing legal mandates with participation levels, voluntary processes had the highest mean rank (mean = 4.3), followed by legally required processes (mean = 3.6) and cases with no information or no applicable legal requirements (i.e., mean = 1.5).

4.3. How do opportunities for participation relate to the models of participation?

Considering the levels of participation, a Spearman correlation evidenced moderate and strong positive correlations, respectively, between the level of participation, the number of opportunities provided, and the score for opportunities (i.e., from insufficient to excellent). There is also a weak positive correlation between legal mandates and the level of participation. No correlation is equal or higher than 0.8, and the p-value for all correlations is 0.05, indicating statistical significance. Higher levels of participation are therefore likely to provide more opportunities for communities to exert their influence through participation. These

Fig. 6. Key moments when participation occurs throughout wind energy project stages.

correlations are shown in Fig. 8, which also provides the Spearman correlation coefficients.

To further explore the relationships between the level of participation (i.e., ranked from alibi participation, with a score of 1, to cooperation, with a score of 6) and the ranked score for opportunities for participation (from insufficient, with a score of 1 to excellent with a score of 5), a bivariate ordered logit model was applied. The dependent variable is “opportunities for participation”, and the independent variable is the “level of participation”. The model results indicate that as the level of participation practices increases (i.e., consultation or level 4, financial support or level 5 and cooperation, or level 6), the likelihood of opportunities for participation being higher (i.e., moderate, good, or excellent) also increases. The coefficients for the level score are statistically significant across all categories of opportunities, with p-values less than 0.05, suggesting a strong relationship between participation practices and the perceived quality of opportunities. For instance, the coefficient (3.3326) for opportunities for participation at the rank of 5 suggests a strong positive association between the highest rank of levels of participation and the highest category of perceived opportunities. The pseudo-R-squared value of 0.278 indicates that approximately 27.8 % of the variance in the opportunities for participation can be explained by the level of participation, which is a reasonable fit for a logistic regression. To ensure the robustness of the logit model, outliers were removed from the dataset, therefore, this analysis was applied to 260

observations. The model results are presented in Table 3.

4.4. How do social innovations relate to more inclusive and transparent practices?

SI can lead to more inclusive and transparent participation processes. Except for the ‘private company’ and ‘grassroots opposition’ cases, social innovation initiatives tend to operate based on high levels of participatory engagement. Grassroots opposition is also more common when the installed capacity is high, thus playing a role in evidencing unjust processes (e.g., the Brazil Nordeste case).

The most common type of SI organisational forms are “REScoops” (67 cases) followed by community trust or fund (33 cases), public-private ventures (32 cases), private companies (24 cases), grassroots opposition (18 cases), local government initiatives with citizens (18 cases), and grassroots projects (17 cases).

Examples of REScoops include Belgium’s “Vent d’Enfan” cooperative, where members buy wind project shares on behalf of children or choose to offer their shares to a minor. Similarly to Vent d’Enfan, several cooperatives develop innovative citizen participation models, with social and economic benefits for the participating communities. Another example is the “SeaCoop” cooperative led by a group of 33 citizens, aiming to ensure that offshore wind energy investments deliver returns to local households through lower electricity rates. In Canada, the

Fig. 7. The quality of opportunities for participation.

Chippewas of Georgina Island First Nation established the Pukwis project, a community-owned wind farm with ten 2 MW turbines funded by cooperative members' shares and commercial loans and supported by a Power Purchase Agreement with the Ontario Power Authority. Now fully owned by the community, the project has inspired other First Nation communities to advance in the self-production of renewable energy. Cooperative shareholders follow the 'one-member, one-vote' democratic voting system, with most members being First Nation people, although the minimum share costs exceed 1000 \$.

Viure Del Aire/EOLPOP (Catalonia, Spain) is an example of a private company, in which wind energy installations are owned by citizens investing in the project. The company finds a suitable location, acquires necessary licenses, and chooses the wind turbine model. Investments are open to citizens who can directly work to offset their carbon emissions (i. e., the company is also an example of financial participation, in which citizens act as investors). Individual investment may vary, but the company recommends that they align with each person's daily energy needs and offers a tool for quick calculations based on electricity, thermal, and mobility-related energy requirements.

The "Windfall Fund" is an example of a community fund managed by the Prospects Foundation in Hyndburn. The fund was established based on the revenue of a new wind farm in Hyndburn and is provided by the wind farm's promoter (i.e., EnergieKontor) to be managed by the Foundation, which is a community-owned local charity. The goal of the foundation is to use the fund for sustainable environmental projects that also improve local quality of life. Community groups can apply to fund their projects, which must relate to specific themes (i.e., improving

biodiversity; waste management; sustainable transport; among others), and funding can range from 1000 to 5000 £.

Public-private partnerships can entail highly varied business and organisational models. In Canada, the Burchill Wind Project is co-owned by a private company and by the Tobique First Nation, located along the Tobique River and governed by an elected council. Natural Forces, a private company investing in renewable energy in Canada, Ireland, and France, focuses on establishing partnerships with local communities. While most shares of the project are owned by the Tobique First Nation, Natural Forces holds minor shares. Situated in the traditional lands of the Tobique Nation, the project enables a fair distribution of costs and benefits for First Nation communities.

To analyse the variance in participation levels (i.e., "level score") within different SI, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test was applied. Community trust or fund and REScoops had median participation levels of 5.0, while grassroots projects, public-private partnerships, and local government projects with citizens had medians of 4.0. Private companies had medians of 3.5 and grassroots opposition of 3.0. These differences are statistically significant, with a p-value close to zero (i.e., 2.2×10^{-6}). Fig. 9 shows the boxplots of each of the social innovation initiatives' organisational types. The y-axis represents the level of participation ranging from Alibi (1) to Cooperation (6).

When comparing the type of SI and the technology of the projects, REScoops show diversity in their investments, including two offshore wind projects, two combined offshore with onshore wind projects, 60 cases of onshore wind and 11 small wind projects. Public-private partnerships are also diverse in their investments, including 22 onshore, 6

Fig. 8. Heatmap illustrating correlations between variables that characterise participation.

Table 3

Results of the bivariate ordered logit model of opportunities for participation and the level of participation.

Variables	Coefficient (level of participation)	Standard Error	Z-value (coefficient divided by the standard error. High values suggest statistical significance)	P-value
Opportunities for participation (dependent variable) = 2				
Intercept	-3.9376	1.155	-3.410	0.001
Level of participation	0.8739	0.377	2.320	0.020
Opportunities for participation = 3				
Intercept	-6.3344	1.021	-6.207	0.000
Level of participation	2.1767	0.318	6.849	0.000
Opportunities for participation = 4				
Intercept	-10.2475	1.599	-6.408	0.000
Level of participation	2.6337	0.408	6.449	0.000
Opportunities for participation = 5				
Intercept	-12.7002	1.497	-8.486	0.000
Level of participation	3.3326	0.386	8.639	0.000

offshore and one small wind case. Community trust or fund include 19 onshore wind cases, seven offshore wind cases, and one small wind project. Grassroots opposition initiatives were only found in the context of onshore wind projects (19 cases), while grassroots projects include 14 cases onshore and five offshore wind cases. Private companies have no investments in small wind, with 16 onshore and six offshore wind cases. Likewise, local government initiatives with citizens comprise 16 onshore and two offshore wind cases. These frequencies are illustrated in Fig. 10.

Finally, when comparing SI with installed capacity (with a sample size of 184 cases, after removing outliers), grassroots opposition initiatives coincide with higher installed capacity projects (i.e., mean

installed capacity = 167 Mega Watts), closely followed by grassroots projects (mean = 134 MW). Private companies (mean = 112 MW), public-private partnerships (mean = 111 MW), and community trust or fund (mean = 108 MW) also invest in large projects. However, REScoops, which operate at higher levels of participation, invest in projects with lower installed capacities (mean = 33 MW). Thus, despite the diversity of investments by REScoops, targeted projects are smaller when compared with other SI. Local government projects with citizens also tend to be smaller (mean = 78 MW). Nevertheless, as illustrated by Fig. 11, standard deviations show a wide range of values within each group, consequently, these findings should be interpreted cautiously as

Fig. 9. Boxplot of participation levels by type of social innovation.

they may only indicate the underlying reality.

5. Discussion

This discussion considers how diverse participatory practices in wind energy developments influence energy justice differently, by elaborating on how participatory practices are adopted in wind energy developments, how opportunities for participation link to the models of participation and how SI may be contributing to more inclusive and transparent practices.

Notwithstanding the urgency of advancing the energy transition, it is important to avoid reproducing the unjust procedures of the fossil-fuel based regime [84], ensuring energy justice through careful consideration of the needs and concerns of local populations [85]. Drawing on the ‘ecologies of participation’ framework [7] to analyse participation in the context of wind energy developments, this study has evidenced that not all models of participation are equal in fostering inclusion, transparency and the ability of citizens to influence processes, and benefit fairly from the costs of the transition.

Although participation is widespread across the collected wind energy case studies, there are plenty of shortcomings, and “pseudo-

participation” practices are still common [86]. Higher levels of participation (i.e., financial, cooperation), and practices that entail a wider range of opportunities provided for participatory engagement, are less common than consultation and information-related practices, which are linked to moderate or sufficient opportunities for participation. Practices can range from cooperative investments and community funds, which require a significant engagement of local communities, to donations and in-kind payments, often failing to consult the community on their preferences [12]. Also, in the case of financial participation, there is a significant difference in terms of the value of “fairness” between land lease payments to landowners who make up a restricted group of stakeholders, when compared with setting up a local community fund from which diverse community members may benefit [42]. Likewise, information participation practices can span from website and simple dissemination activities to the institution of a quality label, requiring the implementation of inclusive participatory practices by the promoter [87]. Additionally, within the practices reviewed, participation occurred mainly at the planning stages, and seldomly at other stages of the project. The analysis thus reinforces the need to consider not only how these practices are encouraged, but also when they take place, their specific social, economic and environmental impacts, and who is

Fig. 10. Frequency of social innovation types concerning technology.

involved in the process [8,88].

Furthermore, higher levels such as cooperation and financial participation need to be continuously improved, seeking to positively influence wider spaces of participation grounded on principles of energy justice [24]. These wider spaces can contribute to normalising the importance of offering real possibilities for citizens to collectively shape the development of projects through their participation. The findings equally reinforce the relevance of integrating participatory practices as a strategy to prevent conflict, fostering a transparent engagement in wind energy governance, respecting local knowledge, and acknowledging the concerns of traditional communities [89–91]. Here a higher focus on Global South countries, which is a limitation of this study, would be critical.

With examples related to alibi participation, this study showed that practices which lack inclusivity, and transparency and prevent citizens from influencing projects, are often supported by institutional actors, including governments. Thus, the role of energy constitutions (i.e., institutionalised processes, policy, rules and structures) [92] in limiting fairer participatory practices is significant. Not surprisingly, regulatory frameworks fell short of promoting extensive participatory practices [93], while voluntary processes (i.e., when no legal mandate for participation existed) coincided with higher levels of participation.

Conversely, bottom-up action is advancing energy justice in wind governance, through grassroots opposition and grassroots innovations, drawing attention to recognition justice aspects, co-producing new practices and incentivising new learnings [94].

Social innovation initiatives include participatory practices at higher levels of participation, which likewise provide more opportunities for participation, for instance, through new forms of financial participation (i.e., the Viure Del Aire company). However, not all SI are equal in the ways through which inclusivity, influence and information (transparency) factors ensure fairer procedures [1]. For instance, REScoops offer higher opportunities for participation, adhere to principles of transparency and ensure their members can influence decisions made (e.g., through the cooperatives' one-member, one-vote decision-making model) [31]. However, cooperatives may not be representative of the local community, and often have financial and temporal barriers to joining (i.e. members must invest in the cooperative and have sufficient time to participate), thus limiting the breadth of their inclusiveness. Public-private partnerships may include highly transparent cases but may be less concerned with inclusiveness [19,95].

Evidence equally indicates that larger-sized installations, sometimes subdivided into smaller wind parks for facilitating licensing and environmental assessment processes, as in the case of Brazil [96], may be

Fig. 11. Installed capacity in relation to diverse social innovation initiatives.

associated with fewer opportunities for participation. However, further in-depth case study research is still needed to understand the root causes of opposition to these installations and the relevance of licensing processes in this context. In this study, larger-sized installations have in several cases been at the centre of “grassroots opposition”. Examples include projects affecting Indigenous Peoples’ lands (e.g., Sámi people in Norway; and the Zapotec in Isthmus of Tehuantepec in Mexico) [47, 63]. These opposition cases offer evidence of wind energy developments which not only fail to involve local communities but can also have direct negative impacts on local livelihoods [47].

Lastly, more transparent and inclusive SI, such as cooperatives, mainly invest in middle-sized installations. Thus, it is unclear to what extent Rescoops can contribute to meeting production targets, based on the scale of renewable energy production that is required [97], since these innovations typically invest in projects with low to medium installed capacity. Their transformative potential may instead depend on their capacity to innovate in collective participatory practices and to actively demonstrate how these practices can cater to energy justice principles, such as inclusion, transparency, capacity to influence and shared responsibility for the environment [11]. Hence, the key impact of SI may be in establishing wider spaces for participation that cater to the

inclusive engagement of citizens and communities, while also supporting grassroots projects and opposition in the case of unjust projects [63, 98].

6. Conclusion

Drawing on the ecologies of participation framework, this analysis took stock of a new dataset with examples of participatory practices from various countries across the globe to understand how inclusive participatory practices are adopted in wind energy developments. The study’s exploratory hypotheses were confirmed: higher opportunities for participation are interlinked to the models of participation employed, and projects driven by SI initiatives are more likely to exhibit inclusive and transparent practices. Furthermore, fairer participation practices are also interconnected to the wider spaces of participation and the local energy constitutions in which practices are embedded. The study has equally evidenced that although SIs are more likely to exhibit more inclusive, empowering, and transparent participatory practices, there are also significant differences between initiatives.

The findings highlight that SIs are likely to uphold energy justice principles, such as transparency, inclusiveness and shared responsibility

for the environment. For instance, by enabling citizen investments, REScoops contribute to higher distributive justice. Procedural justice is also enacted through general assemblies, where information is openly shared, and each member has equal voting rights on the decisions made. Recognition justice is relevant in the case of grassroots innovations led by Indigenous Peoples, thus recognising the need to ensure more vulnerable communities are not excluded from new energy developments. Therefore, SI should be protected and incentivised, through regulatory frameworks.

This analysis has relevant implications for industry, policymakers, and the wider research community. First, industry actors need to carefully consider procedurally just approaches when investing in large-scale developments, paying attention to marginalised and vulnerable communities, thus promoting fairness in processes, while helping to prevent protest and opposition movements. Second, policymakers need to provide effective regulatory frameworks that offer benefits to diverse types of SI (e.g., public-private partnerships, grassroots projects) and encourage the direct participation of citizens in land use and energy planning processes through the integration of local knowledge, including traditional knowledge. Energy justice in wind energy developments can be further enhanced through policies that enable citizens' direct participation in co-financing and in the management of new installations. Denmark offers an example of good practice, as the country's Renewable Energy Act requires citizens to hold at least a 20 % share in new wind energy projects, with revenues to be invested in local community projects.

Lastly, for the research community, countries in the Global South represent a minority in the data collected and therefore should be a focus in future research on participation in wind energy projects. In-depth regional comparisons can reveal differences in participatory practices, embedded in diverse cultural and socio-political contexts that may enable or hinder participation. These differences may concern asymmetric power relations between project promoters, investors and local communities, as SI and participation practices require a degree of transparency and accountability which may not always be present in Global South countries. Furthermore, grassroots innovations have been found to play a critical role, both as supporters and opponents of renewable energy projects. Thus, grassroots innovations deserve further attention, considering their potential for effectively addressing local needs through inclusive, and sustainable energy projects.

Future research should also take stock of participatory practices related to other renewable energy technologies, including emergent technologies such as green hydrogen production plans, and large-scale solar energy plants, which are likely to lead to wider debates and local concerns. New policies for the large-scale implementation of renewable energy projects should include participatory processes that fully account for local communities' perspectives. Participatory practices should be capable of integrating citizens' proposals and perspectives throughout the lifecycle of energy projects. Such policies should equally enable processes of negotiation and agreement that work in tandem with environmental impact assessments and licensing procedures.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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